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Species composition and seasonal abundance of some cucurbit insect pests with emphasis on the relative susceptibility of newly produced cabbage and cauliflower cultivars to the prevalent sap-sucking pests in Assiut Governorate, Upper Egypt

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Studying the species composition and seasonal abundance of some cucurbit insect pests, with emphasis on the relative susceptibility of newly produced cabbage and cauliflower cultivars to the prevalent sap-sucking pests in Assiut Governorate, Upper Egypt, was the cornerstone of this investigation. The results revealed 10 arthropod species belonging to 7 families and 4 insect orders in the cabbage and cauliflower plantations. The collected species are divided into 4 groups. The first group contained 5 phytophagous species. The second group contained 1 predatory species. The third group contained 3 predominantly phytophagous (predacious in part) species. However, the fourth group contained 1 parasitoid species. The Hemiptera order contains 40% of the collected species. However, both Thysanoptera and Hymenoptera contained only 10%. Onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), were recorded on cabbage in small numbers at the beginning of the season. A gradual increase in the pest numbers was recorded until its lonely peak on March 5, with 22.81, 20.90, and 21.86 individuals/cabbage leaf during the 2024, 2025, and entire periods of study, respectively. The cabbage aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) was recorded in low numbers on cabbage at the beginning of the season until mid-March by 1-2 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf during the 2024 and 2025 seasons. This insect pest exhibited its lonely peak on April 2 on cabbage by 10.83 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf with a seasonal mean of 5.42 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf during the entire study period. Similar results were recorded for cauliflower. The mean numbers and population percentages of *T. tabaci* on cauliflower were higher than those recorded on cabbage. However, *B. brassicae* presented the opposite results. Regarding the susceptibility degrees, it can be concluded that two cabbage cultivars (Cross El-Fallah and Jumbo Cross Hybrid 1) appeared as susceptible (S) cultivars against both *T. tabaci* and *B. brassicae*. However, the crossing cabbage cultivar and all of the tested cauliflower cultivars showed some resistance against both *T. tabaci* and *B. brassicae*. Therefore, the authors recommend using cultivars that showed some sort of resistance among advanced breeding programs to produce new cultivars resistant to *T. tabaci* and *B. brassicae*.

Introduction

Cabbage is a herbaceous green leafy vegetable belonging to the Brassicaceae family, along with several other crop species, including broccoli, kale, cauliflower, and kohlrabi (Katz and Weaver, 2003). Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L) is an excellent source of a variety of vitamins, minerals, and dietary fiber (Adeniji *et al.*, 2010) and has been ranked by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) among the top 20 vegetable crops grown worldwide, establishing it as an important food source globally (FAO, 1988). The minerals, vitamins, and anti-nutrient composition of *B. oleracea* was evaluated by Ogbede *et al.* (2015) to educate people about the massive nutrients inherent in this vegetable and serve as a useful tool for nutritionists to formulate balanced diets. Cabbage plantations have been subjected to attacks by several key insect pests, such as the aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) (Embaby and Lotfy, 2015). Aphids damaged cabbage both directly and indirectly. The feeding of adults and nymphs directly harms plants, whereas indirect damage can result from the secretion of honeydew, transmission of plant diseases, and contamination of the harvested crop (Liu and Sparks, 2001). A total of 22 insect species were found feeding on different parts of cauliflower plants (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*) at some stage of their life cycle. The species are distributed in five insect

orders: Coleoptera (7), Lepidoptera (6), Hemiptera (6), Diptera (2), and Thysanoptera (1) (Farrugia, 1997). Conversely, resistant host plants often have a higher economic threshold level than susceptible cultivars and are highly stable because they do not provide any selection pressure on pest populations to evolve virulence. Thus, they are useful in preventing the development of insect biotypes (Heinrichs, 1986). This investigation aims to determine the following: (1) Species composition of arthropod pests and natural enemies inhabiting cabbage and cauliflower plantations in Assiut, Upper Egypt; (2) Seasonal abundance of sap-sucking pests in cabbage and cauliflower leaves; and (3) Relative susceptibility of some newly produced cabbage and cauliflower cultivars against the main sap-sucking insect pests.

Materials and methods

Experimental area

Field experiments were conducted during the two successive seasons of 2024 and 2025 in the experimental farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Assiut University (about 400 km south of Cairo), Assiut Governorate, Egypt. An area of about (252m²) was cultivated on January 1 in both seasons by cabbage and cauliflower cultivars (Table 1) obtained from El-Salam Arboretum (Assiut). The experimental area was divided into plots of approximately 10.5 m². All the recommended agricultural practices were performed normally. The pesticide treatments were completely prevented.

Table (1): Tested cabbage and cauliflower cultivars.

Trade name	Country of Origin	Imported by
Cabbage cultivars		
1. Cabbage hybrid crossina	Japan	Fine seeds Int. SAE
2. Cross El-Fallah	Jordan	Fine seeds Int. SAE
3. Jumbo Cross Hybrid 1	Chile	Calyx Seed (Italy)
Cauliflower cultivars		
1.Sky Doker	U.S.A.	Fine seeds Int. SAE
2.HY. Biasira	China	Horus Agro
3.Bonny	Chile	Technogreen

1. Sampling techniques:

Two sampling methods have been used to encounter arthropods inhabitants of cabbage and cauliflower plantations throughout two successive growing seasons (2024 and 2025). These methods included the use of yellow sticky traps and direct count (visual observations). Sampling started from mid-February to the first of April during each growing season.

1.1. Yellow sticky traps:

The sticky traps were made of yellow, opaque polyvinyl material (peak reflectance wavelength 57 nm) measuring 20.5 x 10 cm, covered with a strongly diluted, sticky paste base (Polyisobutene), so that the surface was tacky but not thick, as recommended by Gerling and Horowitz (1984). The traps were vertically placed on the top of wooden stalks 15 cm above the plants, fitted with large wooden clips in the center of each plot. The traps were collected weekly and examined in the laboratory using a stereomicroscope. The collected specimens were counted and preserved for identification.

1.2. Direct count method (Visual observations):

The direct count method was used to record the numbers of thrips and cabbage aphids inhabiting the outer cabbage and cauliflower leaves at weekly intervals, as described by Varmora *et al.* (2009). Four cabbage and 4 cauliflower leaves (1 leaf/plant)/each replicate (4 replicates)/each cultivar was randomly picked up from 4 infested plants and transferred to the laboratory in muslin bags for later examination. The mean numbers of *T. tabaci* (adults + nymphs) were counted per leaf, and *B. brassicae* (all forms) were counted/5 inches²/leaf, six weeks after transplantation until harvesting.

2. Species composition of arthropod pests and natural enemies inhabiting cucurbit plantations:

Weekly samples were randomly collected 6 weeks after transplantation and continued until harvesting, whereas one yellow sticky trap/plot (10.5 m²) was used. Each sample collected was transferred to the laboratory. The number of species in each sample was recorded as reported by Abdel-Galil and Amro (2014). The collected insect species were identified by specialists of the Insect Classification Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center.

3. Seasonal abundance of the main cabbage and cauliflower sap-sucking insect pests:

To determine the seasonal abundance of arthropod pests inhabiting cabbage and cauliflower plants, leaf sampling was performed. Samples of 4 cabbage and 4 cauliflower leaves were randomly collected weekly for each cabbage and cauliflower cultivar from each experimental unit (4 replicates), 6 weeks after transplantation, for 8 weeks. Samples were kept in polyethylene bags until thoroughly examined in the laboratory using a stereomicroscope. The number of thrips (adults + nymphs) and cabbage aphids (all forms) within each sample /cultivar was counted and recorded as previously described by Yuliadhi *et al.* (2015) and Salem *et al.* (2018). Collected specimens were preserved for later identification.

4. Relative susceptibility of cabbage and cauliflower cultivars to the main sap-sucking insect pests:

The mean numbers of the targeted species were used to determine the relative susceptibility degrees of the tested cabbage and cauliflower cultivars as described by Chiang and Talekar (1980) equation. The degree of relative susceptibility was dependent on the general mean number of the pest (\bar{X}) and the standard deviation (SD). Cultivars with mean numbers more than $\bar{X}+2SD$ were considered highly

susceptible (HS); between \bar{X} and $\bar{X}+2SD$, susceptible (S); between \bar{X} and $\bar{X}-SD$, low resistant (LR); between $\bar{X}-SD$ and $\bar{X}-2SD$, moderately resistant (MR); and less than $\bar{X}-2SD$ were considered highly resistant (HR).

Results and discussion

1. Species composition of arthropod pests and natural enemies inhabiting cucurbit plantations:

The data presented in Table (2) revealed 10 arthropod species belonging to 7 families and 4 insect orders in association with cabbage and cauliflower plantations. The collected species were divided into 4 groups. The first group contained 5 phytophagous species. The second group contained 1 predatory species. The third group contained 3 predominantly phytophagous (Predacious in part) species. However, the fourth group contained 1 parasitoid species. The order Hemiptera contained 40% of the collected insects. However, both Thysanoptera and Hymenoptera contained only 10%. The abovementioned identification is dependent on that classified according to Bourgoin and Campbell (2002) and Amro *et al.* (2016).

Intensive and extensive observations indicated that species collected during this study can be classified as sucking pests, predators, and parasitoids. Yellow sticky traps were the most suitable method for collecting all insect

pests infesting cabbage and cauliflower. However, the direct count method was the most suitable method for collecting cabbage aphids and their parasitoids. This finding agrees with those obtained by Amro *et al.* (2017).

In this approach, Kant *et al.* (2023) identified 14 species of insect pests, including natural enemies, on cabbage in Western Uttar Pradesh. Six orders of insects were observed, with Lepidoptera being the most predominant, accounting for approximately 43% of the total insect species. The orders Coleoptera, Hemiptera, and Hymenoptera were responsible for approximately 14% of insect pests and natural enemies, respectively. During the study conducted by Singh *et al.* (2024), many insects damaged the cauliflower crop, such as the tobacco caterpillar, *Spodoptera litura* (Fab.), the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (Linn.); the stem borer, *Hellula undalis* (Fabricius); the cauliflower aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* (Linnaeus), the mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kaltenbach); the leaf webber, *Crocidolomia binotatus* (Zeller); and the painted bug, *Bagrada cruciferum* (Kirk.). The tobacco caterpillar, *Spodoptera litura*, and the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella*, are the major insect pests of cauliflower and are responsible for major crop yield losses.

Table (2): A partial taxonomic list of arthropod pests and natural enemies collected from and around cabbage and cauliflower plantations during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons at Assiut using direct count and yellow sticky traps.

Order and family	Scientific name	Status and frequency	Sampling method
Thysanoptera			
Thripidae (Cotton/Onion thrips)	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> Lindeman, 1889	Phytophagous (F)	Direct count and yellow sticky traps
Hemiptera-Heteroptera			
Anthocoridae (Minute pirate bugs)	<i>Orius</i> spp.	Predator (R)	Yellow sticky traps
Miridae (plant or leaf bugs)	<i>Campylomma impicta</i> Wagner, 1956	Phytophagous (predator in part) (R)	Yellow sticky traps
	<i>Creontiades pallidus</i> (Rambur, 1839)	Phytophagous (predator in part) (R)	Yellow sticky traps
	<i>Nesidiocoris tenuis</i> (Reuter, 1895)	Phytophagous (predator in part) (R)	Yellow sticky traps
Homoptera			
Aleyrodidae (Whiteflies)	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (Gennadius, 1889)	Phytophagous (F)	Yellow sticky traps
Cicadellidae (leaf hoppers)	<i>Empoasca</i> spp.	Phytophagous (F)	Yellow sticky traps
Aphididae (Aphids)	<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Phytophagous (F)	Direct count and yellow sticky traps
	<i>Myzus persicae</i> (Sulzer, 1776)	Phytophagous (F)	Direct count and yellow sticky traps
Hymenoptera Aphidiidae (Parasitoid wasps)	<i>Diaeretiella rapae</i> (McIntoch, 1855)	Parasitoid (HF)	Direct count and yellow sticky traps

F = frequent; HF= high frequency; R = rare

2. Seasonal abundance of the main cabbage and cauliflower sap-sucking insect pests:

2.1. *Thrips tabaci*:

The data presented in Table (3) expressed the mean numbers of *Thrips tabaci* inhabiting cabbage and cauliflower plants during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons in Assiut Governorate. The pest was recorded on cabbage in low numbers at the beginning of the season by 2.73, 3.46, and 3.09 individuals/leaf during the 2024, 2025, and entire periods of study, respectively. A gradual increase in the pest numbers was recorded until its lonely peak on March 5 with 22.81, 20.90, and 21.85 individuals/cabbage leaf during the 2024 and 2025 seasons and the entire study period, respectively. A sudden decrease in pest numbers was recorded until harvesting. It should be noted that *T. tabaci* recorded its seasonal mean by 9.89, 9.68, and 9.79 individuals/cabbage leaf during the 2024 and 2025 seasons and the entire study period, respectively. Quite similar *T. tabaci* population values were recorded on cauliflower. The seasonal general mean of *T. tabaci* on cauliflower (11.14 individuals/leaf)

was recorded to be 1.14-fold of that recorded on cabbage (9.79 individuals/leaf). However, the percentages of pest populations on the examined cauliflower leaves throughout the entire study period (53.23%) were 1.18-fold of that recorded on cabbage. F value between *T. tabaci* populations during inspection dates in both study seasons revealed highly significant values. Therefore, it can be concluded that the mean numbers and population percentages of *T. tabaci* on cauliflower were higher than those recorded on cabbage. In agreement with these results, in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, El-Fakharany (2010) reported that population fluctuations of *T. tabaci* reached maximal abundance in March and early April in both the 2008/09 and 2009/10 seasons to attack cabbage plants. Amongst twenty arthropod species, belonging to fifteen families and six orders, Abdel-Galil *et al.* (2021) recorded *Thrips tabaci*, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Empoasca* sp., and *Aphis craccivora* as the highest dominant species inhabiting cabbage plantations during the 2018 and 2019 seasons in Assiut, Upper Egypt.

Table (3): Mean numbers of *Thrips tabaci* ^(a) inhabiting cabbage and cauliflower plants during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons in Assiut Governorate.

Inspection date	Mean number of <i>Thrips tabaci</i> (Adults+nymphs)/leaf of cabbage			Mean number of <i>Thrips tabaci</i> (Adults+nymphs)/cauliflower leaf			Grand mean of <i>Thrips tabaci</i> /Cauliflower and cauliflower leaves 2024& 2025	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> % on Cabbage	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> % on cauliflower
	2024	2025	2024 and 2025	2024	2025	2024 and 2025			
	Mean±SD	Mean± SD	Grand Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Grand Mean±SD			
Feb., 13	2.73±1.59c	3.46±1.46c	3.09±1.53	2.83±2.26d	4.10±2.01c	3.47±2.14	6.56	47.18	52.82
Feb., 20	12.54±3.68b	12.94±3.16b	12.74±3.42	12.96±12.06b	11.21±11.20b	12.08±11.63	24.82	51.33	48.71
Feb., 27	21.54±8.38a	20.38±7.29a	20.96±7.84	20.88±12.60a	23.71±10.70a	22.29±11.65	43.25	48.45	51.55
Mar., 5	22.81±7.99a	20.90±8.35a	21.85±8.17	25.48±14.13a	27.00±13.40a	26.24±13.76	48.09	45.45	54.55
Mar., 12	11.31±2.96b	8.54±4.45c	9.93±3.70	8.31±3.20bc	9.79±3.20b	9.05±3.20	18.98	52.32	47.68
Mar., 19	3.90±3.24c	5.04±2.53d	4.47±2.89	9.83±7.41b	10.23±7.22b	10.03±7.31	14.50	30.83	69.17
Mar., 26	2.73±2.2c	3.69±2.9d	3.21±2.55	3.52±2.81cd	4.10±2.79c	3.81±2.80	7.02	45.73	54.27
Apr., 2	1.58±0.77	2.50±2.22d	2.04±1.49	1.73±1.18d	2.50±1.49c	2.11±1.33	4.15	49.04	50.96
Mean	9.89±9.3	9.68±8.46	9.79±8.88	10.69±11.73	11.58±11.58	11.14±11.66	20.93	46.77	53.23
F-value=	162.91**	125.597**		49.609**	64.632**				

(a) Based on 1 leaf.

(b) Means followed by the same liter in each column are not significantly different at a probability level of 0.05.

2.2. *Brevicoryne brassicae*:

The data presented in Table (4) expresses the mean numbers of cabbage aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* inhabiting cabbage and cauliflower plants during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons in Assiut Governorate. The pest was recorded in low numbers on cabbage at the beginning of the season until mid-March by 1-2 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf during the 2024 and 2025 seasons. On March 19, the pest recorded a sudden increase in its population on cabbage leaves by 8.85, 8.50, and 8.68 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf during the 2024 and 2025 seasons and the entire study period, respectively. This insect pest exhibited its lonely peak on April 2 on cabbage by 10.83 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf with a seasonal mean of 5.42 individuals/1 inch²/cabbage leaf during the entire study period. Before harvesting, the pest showed a sudden decrease in population on cabbage leaves. A similar trend of *B. brassicae* population was recorded on cauliflower plants during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons. Also, it can be noted that the populations of *B. brassicae* on cabbage leaves were 1.55, 2.81, 4.71, and 7.90-fold of that recorded on cauliflower

leaves on March 12, March 19, March 26, and April 2, respectively. In general, the pest population on cabbage was 2.39-fold higher than that on cauliflower. F-value between *B. brassicae* populations during inspection dates in both study seasons revealed highly significant values. Factors responsible for this finding could be those obtained from Ahmed *et al.* (2022). They studied the preference and performance of *Myzus persicae* on three major Brassicaceae vegetables and measured nutrient (Amino acids) and defensive metabolites (Glucosinolates) in these plants. They found that *M. persicae* preferred and performed better on Chinese cabbage than cabbage and radish, which may be due to the relatively higher concentration of amino acids and lower levels of indole glucosinolates in their leaves. These results suggest that both amino acids and glucosinolates in plants may play an important role in the preference and performance of *M. persicae*, providing new knowledge for the cultivation and breeding of Brassicaceae vegetables. This finding confirms those obtained in this manuscript about variations and duplication of *B. brassicae* numbers on cabbage compared to those recorded on cauliflower.

Table (4): Mean numbers of *Brevicoryne brassicae* ^(a) inhabiting cabbage and cauliflower plants during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons in Assiut Governorate.

Inspection date	Mean number <i>B. brassicae</i> (all forms)/1 inch ² /cabbage leaf			Mean number <i>B. brassicae</i> (all forms)/1 inch ² /cauliflower leaf			Grand mean of <i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i> / cabbage and cauliflower leaves in 2024 and 2025	<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i> % on Cabbage	<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i> % on cauliflower
	2024	2025	2024 and 2025	2024	2025	2024 and 2025			
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Grand Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Grand Mean±SD			
Feb., 13	1.54±0.80c	1.67±0.72c	1.61±0.76	0.58±0.50e	1.23±0.42e	0.91±0.46	2.52	63.89	36.11
Feb., 20	1.56±1.01c	2.19±0.98c	1.88±1.00	0.81±0.53de	2.50±1.03cd	1.66±0.78	3.54	53.11	46.89
Feb., 27	1.63±0.87c	2.52±1.17c	2.07±1.02	2.29±1.17ab	3.08±1.60abc	2.69±1.38	4.76	43.61	56.39
Mar., 5	1.71±1.22c	2.96±1.47c	2.33±1.35	1.88±1.70bc	3.79±1.84ab	2.84±1.77	5.16	45.17	54.83
Mar., 12	1.92±1.29c	8.50±5.17b	5.21±3.23	2.77±1.78a	3.92±1.51a	3.35±1.65	8.55	60.86	39.14
Mar., 19	8.85±5.78b	8.50±5.15b	8.68±5.27	2.23±1.51ab	3.92±1.51a	3.08±1.51	11.75	73.81	26.19
Mar., 26	11.5±5.78a	10.00±5.21b	10.75±5.5	1.31±0.59cd	3.25±1.08abc	2.28±0.84	13.03	82.50	17.50
Apr., 2	9.31±4.22b	12.35±5.16a	10.83±4.69	0.75±0.53de	1.98±0.81ed	1.36±0.67	12.19	88.77	11.23
Mean	4.75±5.18	6.09±5.41	5.42±5.3	1.58±1.39	2.96±1.59	2.27±1.49	7.69	70.48	29.52
F-value=	83.822**	60.404**		24.219**	27.384**				

(a) Based on 1 leaf.

(b) Means followed by the same liter in each column are not significantly different at a probability level of 0.05.

3. Relative susceptibility of cabbage and cauliflower cultivars to the main sap-sucking insect pests:

The data presented in Table (5) expressed susceptibility degrees of cabbage and cauliflower cultivars against *Thrips tabaci* and *Brevicoryne brassicae* in Assiut during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons. With respect to the susceptibility degrees, which depended on the pests' mean numbers (\bar{X}) and the standard deviation (SD), the tested cauliflower cultivars showed some sort of resistance against *T. tabaci* and appeared as moderately resistant (MR) cultivars. However, the cabbage cultivar (Cabbage Hybrid Crossina) only appeared as a low-resistant (LR) cultivar against *T. tabaci*. Conversely, the cabbage cultivars (Cross El-Fallah and Jumbo Cross Hybrid 1) appeared as susceptible (S) cultivars against *T. tabaci*. Regarding the cabbage aphid *B. brassicae*, all of the tested cauliflower cultivars and the cabbage cultivar (Cabbage Hybrid Crossina) presented some resistance against this insect pest. However, Cross El-Fallah and Jumbo Cross Hybrid 1 appeared as susceptible (S) cultivars against this insect pest. The F value between cabbage cultivars

attacked by *B. brassicae* was highly significant (23.45). Therefore, it can be concluded that two cabbage cultivars (Cross El-Fallah and Jumbo Cross Hybrid 1) appeared as susceptible (S) cultivars against both *T. tabaci* and *B. brassicae*. However, the remaining cabbage and cauliflower cultivars showed some resistance against both *T. tabaci* and *B. brassicae*. Therefore, the authors recommend using cultivars that showed some sort of resistance among advanced breeding programs to select new cultivars resistant to *T. tabaci* and *B. brassicae*. The varietal resistance of cabbage against the cabbage aphid *B. brassicae* was evaluated by several authors, e.g., Jatoi *et al.* (2001) in Pakistan and Khattab (2007) in Egypt. The resistance of nine cabbage cultivars to cabbage aphid (*B. brassicae*) was studied in greenhouse experiments by Munthali (2009). He reported that cabbage aphids caused 85% leaf damage in the most susceptible cultivar and only 30.9% leaf damage in the more resistant cultivar, which had the lowest number of aphids per leaf, indicating the antibiosis mechanism of resistance to *B. brassicae*.

Table (5): Degrees of susceptibility of cabbage and cauliflower cultivars to the main sap-sucking pests in Assiut during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons.

Inspection year	Annual mean number of pests and susceptibility degrees											
	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> /leaf						<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i> /1/ 1 inch ² /leaf					
	Cabbage			Cauliflower			Cabbage			Cauliflower		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
2024	8.84a	10.51a	10.33a	10.40a	11.85a	9.83a	2.38b	5.53a	6.35a	1.58a	1.60a	1.55a
2025	8.87a	10.74a	9.43a	11.77a	12.08a	10.90a	3.18b	7.09a	7.98a	2.73b	2.89b	3.26a
Mean 2024&2025	8.56	10.63	9.88	11.09	11.97	10.37	2.78	6.31	7.17	2.16	2.25	2.41
Grand Mean	9.69±1.05			11.14±0.80			5.42±2.33			2.27±0.13		
F	1.235			1.012			23.45**			0.036		
Susceptibility degrees	LR	S	S	MR	MR	MR	MR	S	S	LR	LR	MR

Cabbage cultivars: 1-Cabbage Hybrid Crossina, 2-Cross El-Fallah, 3-Jumbo Cross Hybrid 1

Cauliflower cultivars: 1-Sky Doker, 2-HY. Biasira, and 3-Bonny

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